

The Chromatic Number of the Arbitrary Connection of Complete Graphs

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[**INTRODUCTION**]. Research on graph coloring has largely concentrated on various variants of the chromatic number (such as distance coloring, edge coloring...). Research on the traditional chromatic number has mostly focused on upper and lower bounds of the chromatic number, or on defining a graph class by its chromatic number and then studying its properties. The most successful example is perfect graphs. Other related directions include converting graphs into polynomials and studying the eigenvalues of adjacency matrices.

For graph operations we mainly have Join, Cartesian Product, Tensor Product, Strong Product, Lexicographic Product.

For the join of two graphs, the chromatic number is the sum of the chromatic numbers of the two original graphs, but the connections between graphs are usually not complete. This paper focuses on the impact of arbitrary connections on the chromatic number of graphs; we can say it is the “arbitrary connections” of two graphs, especially complete graphs, and establishes some formal necessary and sufficient conditions regarding the chromatic number and the clique number. Obviously, the arbitrary connection is a natural graph operation.

[**ABSTRACT**] This article uses Hall's condition to prove that the chromatic number of arbitrary connection between two complete graphs is equal to the clique number, and establishes the relationship between arbitrary connection between complete graphs and quadratic forms.

[**KEY WORDS**] arbitrary connections; complete graph; chromatic number; clique number; Hall's condition

[**NOTATION**]. For a finite set S , $|S|$ denotes its cardinality. For sets S_1, S_2 , the difference is $S_2 \setminus S_1 = S_2 \cap S_1^c$. For a map $f : S_1 \rightarrow S_2$, define $f(S_1) = \{y \in S_2 : \exists x \in S_1, y = f(x)\}$. For a graph G and a subgraph $P \subseteq G$, $G - P$ means deleting the vertices

of P from G . In this article we consider simple graphs (no loops, no multiple edges), and “graph coloring” refers to vertex coloring (not edge coloring). If $S_2 \subseteq S_1$ and $f : S_1 \rightarrow S_3$, then $f|_{S_2}$ denotes the restriction of f to S_2 .

1 Calculate the chromatic number using Hall’s condition

DEF $G = (V(G), E(G))$ is a graph, $V(G)$ are the vertices of G , $E(G)$ are edges of G ; the complement graph of G is denoted by \overline{G} , which means

$$V(\overline{G}) = V(G),$$

$$\forall a, b \in V(\overline{G}), ab \in E(\overline{G}) \iff ab \notin E(G).$$

$\omega(G)$ is the clique number of G , $\alpha(G)$ is the independence number of G ;
 $\forall P$ is a graph, if $V(P) \subseteq V(G)$, $E(P) \subseteq E(G)$, $\forall a, b \in V(P)$, $ab \in E(P) \iff ab \in E(G)$
we say P is a subgraph of G ;
if $\forall a, b \in V(G)$, $\exists ab \in E(G)$, then we say G is a complete graph;
If $\exists P \subseteq G$ is a subgraph of G , P is a complete graph, then we say P is a complete subgraph;
 $c : V(G) \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}^+$ is a function, if it satisfies $\forall a, b \in V(G)$, $ab \in E(G) \Rightarrow c(a) \neq c(b)$,
we say c is a coloring of G or c is a coloring of $V(G)$.

$$\chi(G) = \min \left\{ c(G) : c \text{ is a coloring of } G \right\}$$

is denoted by $\chi(G)$, $\chi(G)$ is called the chromatic number of G .

LEMMA (Hall’s condition). A bipartite graph has a matching that saturates X if and only if Hall’s condition holds: for every subset $S \subseteq X$, one has $|N(S)| \geq |S|$.

PROPOSITION Let G' be a graph and let $G \subseteq G'$ be a subgraph of G' . If $K_n \subseteq G'$ is a complete subgraph of G' , we may assume that $V(K_n) = \{x_1, \dots, x_n\}$.

For $1 \leq i \leq n$, let

$$L(x_i) = \{a \in V(G) : ax_i \in E(G')\},$$

$V(G) \cup V(K_n) = V(G')$, $V(G) \cap V(K_n) = \emptyset$, Let $c : V(G) \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}^+$ be a coloring of G . Consider extensions $c' : V(G') \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}^+$ such that $c'|_{V(G)} = c$. Then

$$\min \left\{ |c'(V(G'))| : c'|_{V(G)} = c \right\} = \max \left\{ |c(G)|, \max_{1 \leq k \leq n, \{i_1, \dots, i_k\} \subseteq \{1, \dots, n\}} \left\{ \left| \bigcap_{p=1}^k c(L(x_{i_p})) \right| + k \right\} \right\}$$

PROOF. K_n is m -colorable as a subgraph $\iff \exists$ a set of colors T s.t $c(K_n) \subseteq T$ and $|T| \leq m$.

(1)if

$$|c(G)| \geq \max_{1 \leq k \leq n, \{i_1, \dots, i_k\} \subseteq \{1, \dots, n\}} \left\{ \left| \bigcap_{p=1}^k c(L(x_{i_p})) \right| + k \right\}$$

let $T=c(G)$ then

$\forall c'$ is a coloring of G' s.t $c'|_{V(G)} = c$ where c is the coloring of G

$$\iff \forall a \in V(G), b \in K_n, ab \in E(G') \implies c'(a) \neq c'(b) \text{ and } \forall a, b \in K_n, ab \in E(K_n) \implies c'(a) \neq c'(b)$$

$$\iff \forall a \in V(G), b \in K_n, ab \in E(G') \implies c(a) \neq c'(b) \text{ and } \forall a, b \in K_n, ab \in E(K_n) \implies c'(a) \neq c'(b)$$

$$\iff \forall 1 \leq i, j \leq n, i \neq j, c'(x_i) \neq c'(x_j) \text{ and } \forall 1 \leq i \leq n, c'(x_i) \notin c(L(x_i))$$

$$\iff \forall 1 \leq i, j \leq n, i \neq j, c'(x_i) \neq c'(x_j) \text{ and } \forall 1 \leq i \leq n, c'(x_i) \in T - c(L(x_i)) = c(G) - c(L(x_i))$$

$$\iff \text{a matching that saturates } \{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n\} \text{ exists}$$

$$\iff \forall 1 \leq k \leq n, \forall \{i_1, i_2, \dots, i_k\} \subseteq \{1, 2, \dots, n\}, \left| \bigcup_{p=1}^k (c(G) - c(L(x_{i_p}))) \right| \geq k.$$

$$\forall 1 \leq k \leq n, \forall \{i_1, i_2, \dots, i_k\} \subseteq \{1, 2, \dots, n\}, \iff \left| \left(\bigcap_{p=1}^k c(L(x_{i_p})) \right)^c \right| \geq k$$

$$\forall 1 \leq k \leq n, \forall \{i_1, i_2, \dots, i_k\} \subseteq \{1, 2, \dots, n\}, \iff c(G) - \left| \left(\bigcap_{p=1}^k c(L(x_{i_p})) \right)^c \right| \geq k$$

$$\iff |c(G)| \geq \max_{1 \leq k \leq n, \{i_1, \dots, i_k\} \subseteq \{1, \dots, n\}} \left\{ \left| \bigcap_{p=1}^k c(L(x_{i_p})) \right| + k \right\}$$

consider

$$\min \left\{ |c'(V(G'))| : c'|_{V(G)} = c \right\} \leq |c(G) \cup T| = c(G); \min \left\{ |c'(V(G'))| : c'|_{V(G)} = c \right\} \geq c(G)$$

$$\min \left\{ |c'(V(G'))| : c'|_{V(G)} = c \right\} = c(G) = \max \left\{ |c(G)|, \max_{1 \leq k \leq n, \{i_1, \dots, i_k\} \subseteq \{1, \dots, n\}} \left\{ \left| \bigcap_{p=1}^k c(L(x_{i_p})) \right| + k \right\} \right\}$$

which proves the claimed proposition.

(2)if

$$|c(G)| < \max_{1 \leq k \leq n, \{i_1, \dots, i_k\} \subseteq \{1, \dots, n\}} \left\{ \left| \bigcap_{p=1}^k c(L(x_{i_p})) \right| + k \right\}$$

from (1) we know $c(G)$ is not enough ,thus $\forall c'$ is a coloring of G' s.t $c'|_{V(G)} = c$, $c'(G') \geq c(G)$

$$\min \{ |c'(G')| : c'|_{V(G)} = c \} = \min \{ |c'(K_n) \cup c(G)| : c'|_{V(G)} = c \}$$

$$= \min \{ |T| : \exists c' \text{ is a coloring of } K_n, c'(K_n) \subseteq T \text{ and } c(G) \subseteq T \}$$

then similarly,

c' is a coloring of G' s.t $c'|_{V(G)} = c$ where c is the coloring of G

$$\iff \forall 1 \leq k \leq n, \forall \{i_1, i_2, \dots, i_k\} \subseteq \{1, 2, \dots, n\}, \left| \bigcup_{p=1}^k (T - c(L(x_{i_p}))) \right| \geq k.$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \iff |T| \geq \max_{1 \leq k \leq n, \{i_1, \dots, i_k\} \subseteq \{1, \dots, n\}} \left\{ \left| \bigcap_{p=1}^k c(L(x_{i_p})) \right| + k \right\} \\
\min\{|c'(G')| : c'|_{V(G)}\} &= \min\{|T| : c'(K_n) \subseteq T \text{ and } c(G) \subseteq T\} \\
&= \min\{|T| : c(G) \subseteq T \text{ and } |T| \geq \max_{1 \leq k \leq n, \{i_1, \dots, i_k\} \subseteq \{1, \dots, n\}} \left\{ \left| \bigcap_{p=1}^k c(L(x_{i_p})) \right| + k \right\}\} \\
&= \max_{1 \leq k \leq n, \{i_1, \dots, i_k\} \subseteq \{1, \dots, n\}} \left\{ \left| \bigcap_{p=1}^k c(L(x_{i_p})) \right| + k \right\} \\
&= \max\{|c(G)|, \max_{1 \leq k \leq n, \{i_1, \dots, i_k\} \subseteq \{1, \dots, n\}} \left\{ \left| \bigcap_{p=1}^k c(L(x_{i_p})) \right| + k \right\}\}
\end{aligned}$$

DEDUCTION 1 Consider a graph G' . Suppose $G, K_n \subseteq G'$ and

$$V(G) \cup V(K_n) = V(G'), V(G) \cap V(K_n) = \phi$$

Then

$$\chi(G') = \chi(G)$$

if and only if there exists a coloring c of G such that

$$|c(V(G))| \geq \max_{1 \leq k \leq n, \{i_1, \dots, i_k\} \subseteq \{1, \dots, n\}} \left\{ \left| \bigcap_{p=1}^k c(L(x_{i_p})) \right| + k \right\},$$

and

$$|c(V(G))| = \chi(G).$$

PROOF.

- (1) If $\chi(G') = \chi(G)$, then there exists an optimal coloring c_0 of G' with $|c_0(V(G'))| = \chi(G') = \chi(G)$. Restricting to G , let $c = c_0|_{V(G)}$, then c is a coloring of G and $|c(V(G))| = |c_0|_{V(G)}(G) \leq |c_0(V(G'))| = \chi(G)$. on the other hand, $|c(V(G))| \geq \chi(G)$ so we have $|c(V(G))| = \chi(G)$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \max\{|c(V(G))|, \max_{1 \leq k \leq n, \{i_1, \dots, i_k\} \subseteq \{1, \dots, n\}} \left\{ \left| \bigcap_{p=1}^k c(L(x_{i_p})) \right| + k \right\}\} \\
&= \min\{|c'(G')| : c'|_{V(G)} = c\} \leq |c_0(V(G'))| = \chi(G) = |c(V(G))| \\
&\implies \max_{1 \leq k \leq n, \{i_1, \dots, i_k\} \subseteq \{1, \dots, n\}} \left\{ \left| \bigcap_{p=1}^k c(L(x_{i_p})) \right| + k \right\} \leq |c(V(G))|
\end{aligned}$$

- (2) Conversely, if there exists a coloring c of G with $|c(V(G))| = \chi(G)$ and the inequality above holds, then

$$\chi(G) = |c(V(G))| = \max\{|c(V(G))|, \max_{1 \leq k \leq n, \{i_1, \dots, i_k\} \subseteq \{1, \dots, n\}} \left\{ \left| \bigcap_{p=1}^k c(L(x_{i_p})) \right| + k \right\}\}$$

$$= \min\{|c'(G')| : c'|_{V(G)} = c\} \geq \min\{|c'(G')|\} = \chi(G')$$

and $\chi(G) \leq \chi(G')$ hence $\chi(G') = \chi(G)$.

DEDUCTION 2 Consider a graph G' . Suppose $G, K_n \subseteq G'$ and

$$V(G) \cup V(K_n) = V(G'), V(G) \cap V(K_n) = \phi$$

, for any integer $q \geq \chi(G)$,

$$G' \text{ is } q\text{-colorable} \iff q \geq \min_{|c(G)| \leq q} \left\{ \max_{1 \leq k \leq n, \{i_1, \dots, i_k\} \subseteq \{1, \dots, n\}} \left| \bigcap_{p=1}^k c(L(x_{i_p})) \right| + k \right\}$$

PROOF. (1) If G' is q -colorable, \exists a coloring c_0 of G' s.t $c_0(G') \leq q$, thus

$$\begin{aligned} q &\geq c_0(G') \geq \min\{|c'(G')| : c'|_{V(G)} = c_0|_{V(G)}\} \\ &= \max\{|c_0(V(G))|, \max_{1 \leq k \leq n, \{i_1, \dots, i_k\} \subseteq \{1, \dots, n\}} \left\{ \left| \bigcap_{p=1}^k c_0(L(x_{i_p})) \right| + k \right\}\} \end{aligned}$$

and $|c_0(V(G))| \leq c_0(G') \leq q$, so we have

$$\begin{aligned} &\min_{|c(G)| \leq q} \left\{ \max_{1 \leq k \leq n, \{i_1, \dots, i_k\} \subseteq \{1, \dots, n\}} \left\{ \left| \bigcap_{p=1}^k c(L(x_{i_p})) \right| + k \right\} \right\} \\ &\leq \max_{1 \leq k \leq n, \{i_1, \dots, i_k\} \subseteq \{1, \dots, n\}} \left\{ \left| \bigcap_{p=1}^k c_0(L(x_{i_p})) \right| + k \right\} \\ &\leq q \end{aligned}$$

(2)

Conversely, suppose

$$\min_{|c(G)| \leq q} \left\{ \max_{1 \leq k \leq n, \{i_1, \dots, i_k\} \subseteq \{1, \dots, n\}} \left(\left| \bigcap_{p=1}^k c(L(x_{i_p})) \right| + k \right) \right\} \leq q.$$

Then there exists a coloring c_0 of G such that $|c_0(V(G))| \leq q$ and

$$\max_{1 \leq k \leq n, \{i_1, \dots, i_k\} \subseteq \{1, \dots, n\}} \left(\left| \bigcap_{p=1}^k c_0(L(x_{i_p})) \right| + k \right) \leq q.$$

Hence

$$\begin{aligned} \chi(G') &= \min\{|c'(G')| : c' \text{ is a coloring of } G'\} \\ &\leq \min\{|c'(G')| : c'|_{V(G)} = c_0\} \\ &= \max\left\{|c_0(V(G))|, \max_{1 \leq k \leq n, \{i_1, \dots, i_k\} \subseteq \{1, \dots, n\}} \left(\left| \bigcap_{p=1}^k c_0(L(x_{i_p})) \right| + k \right) \right\} \\ &\leq q, \end{aligned}$$

so G' is q -colorable.

[REMARK] for the G, G' , and K_n mentioned above

$$\begin{aligned}\chi(G') &= \min\{q : G' \text{ is } q\text{-colorable}\} \\ &= \min\{q : q \geq \min_{|c(G)| \leq q} \left\{ \max_{1 \leq k \leq n, \{i_1, \dots, i_k\} \subseteq \{1, \dots, n\}} \left| \bigcap_{p=1}^k c(L(x_{i_p})) \right| + k \right\}\}\end{aligned}$$

If $\chi(G)$ satisfies the condition, then $\chi(G') = \chi(G)$; if not, for any $q \in \mathbb{Z}^+$ with $q \geq \chi(G)$,

$$\begin{aligned}& \min_{|c(G)| \leq q} \left\{ \max_{1 \leq k \leq n, \{i_1, \dots, i_k\} \subseteq \{1, \dots, n\}} \left(\left| \bigcap_{p=1}^k c(L(x_{i_p})) \right| + k \right) \right\} \\ & \geq \min_{|c(G)| \leq q+1} \left\{ \max_{1 \leq k \leq n, \{i_1, \dots, i_k\} \subseteq \{1, \dots, n\}} \left(\left| \bigcap_{p=1}^k c(L(x_{i_p})) \right| + k \right) \right\},\end{aligned}$$

so the right-hand side decreases while q increases.

[REMARK] Consider a graph G' . If there exist subgraphs $P_1, P_2 \subseteq G'$ such that $V(P_1) \cup V(P_2) = V(G')$, $P_1 \cap P_2 = K_n$ is a complete subgraph, and $\forall a \in V(P_1) \setminus V(K_n)$, $\forall b \in V(P_2) \setminus V(K_n)$, we have $ab \notin E(G')$, then we have the formula

$$\chi(G') = \max\{\chi(P_1), \chi(P_2)\}.$$

Equivalently,

$$\begin{aligned}\chi(G') &= \max\left\{ \min\left\{ q : \min_{|c(P_1 - K_n)| \leq q} \max_{1 \leq k \leq n, \{i_1, \dots, i_k\} \subseteq \{1, \dots, n\}} \left(\left| \bigcap_{p=1}^k c(L(x_{i_p})) \right| + k \right) \leq q \right\}, \right. \\ & \left. \min\left\{ q : \min_{|c(P_2 - K_n)| \leq q} \max_{1 \leq k \leq n, \{i_1, \dots, i_k\} \subseteq \{1, \dots, n\}} \left(\left| \bigcap_{p=1}^k c(L(x_{i_p})) \right| + k \right) \leq q \right\} \right\}.\end{aligned}$$

So it is easier to calculate if K_n is better selected sometimes.

[PROPOSITION] For any graph G' , suppose $G, K_n \subseteq G'$ are subgraphs of G' and K_n is a complete subgraph. $V(G') = V(G) \cup V(K_n)$, $V(G) \cap V(K_n) = \phi$ Then

$$\omega(G') = \max\left\{ \omega(G), \max_{1 \leq k \leq n, \{i_1, \dots, i_k\} \subseteq \{1, \dots, n\}} \left(\omega\left(\bigcap_{p=1}^k L(x_{i_p})\right) + k \right) \right\}.$$

PROOF. (1) Consider any complete subgraph $P \subseteq G'$. $V(P) = \omega(G')$, If $V(P) \cap V(K_n) = \emptyset$, then $P \subseteq G$ and hence $|V(P)| \leq \omega(G)$.

If $V(P) \cap V(K_n) \neq \emptyset$, then there exist $x_{i_1}, \dots, x_{i_k} \in V(K_n)$ and $y_1, \dots, y_{|P|-k} \in V(G)$ such that $V(P) = \{x_{i_1}, \dots, x_{i_k}, y_1, \dots, y_{|P|-k}\}$. By definition, $\{y_1, \dots, y_{|P|-k}\} \subseteq \bigcap_{p=1}^k L(x_{i_p})$ and every two of them are connected, so

$$\omega\left(\bigcap_{p=1}^k L(x_{i_p})\right) \geq |P| - k.$$

Thus

$$\omega(G') = |P| \leq \omega\left(\bigcap_{p=1}^k L(x_{i_p})\right) + k \leq \max_{1 \leq k \leq n, \{i_1, \dots, i_k\} \subseteq \{1, \dots, n\}} \left\{ \omega\left(\bigcap_{p=1}^k L(x_{i_p})\right) + k \right\}.$$

so

$$\omega(G') \leq \max \left\{ \omega(G), \max_{1 \leq k \leq n, \{i_1, \dots, i_k\} \subseteq \{1, \dots, n\}} \left(\omega\left(\bigcap_{p=1}^k L(x_{i_p})\right) + k \right) \right\}$$

(2) Obviously $\omega(G') \geq \omega(G)$. Moreover, for any $1 \leq k \leq n$ and $\{i_1, \dots, i_k\} \subseteq \{1, \dots, n\}$,

$$\omega\left(\bigcap_{p=1}^k L(x_{i_p})\right) \leq \omega\left(\bigcap_{p=1}^k L(x_{i_p}) \cup K_n\right) \leq \omega(G')$$

$$\max_{1 \leq k \leq n, \{i_1, \dots, i_k\} \subseteq \{1, \dots, n\}} \left\{ \omega\left(\bigcap_{p=1}^k L(x_{i_p})\right) + k \right\} \leq \omega(G')$$

so

Hence

$$\begin{aligned} & \max \left\{ \omega(G), \max_{1 \leq k \leq n, \{i_1, \dots, i_k\} \subseteq \{1, \dots, n\}} \left(\omega\left(\bigcap_{p=1}^k L(x_{i_p})\right) + k \right) \right\} \leq \omega(G') \\ \implies & \max \left\{ \omega(G), \max_{1 \leq k \leq n, \{i_1, \dots, i_k\} \subseteq \{1, \dots, n\}} \left(\omega\left(\bigcap_{p=1}^k L(x_{i_p})\right) + k \right) \right\} = \omega(G') \end{aligned}$$

REMARK Then we can see the consistency between the clique number and the chromatic number.

[DEF] Consider a graph G . If there exists a coloring $c : V(G) \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}^+$ such that for any $a, b \in V(G)$,

$$ab \in E(G) \iff c(a) \neq c(b),$$

we say G is a *special perfect graph*, and c is a *special coloring* of G .

[PROPERTIES 1] If c is a special coloring of a special perfect graph G , then

$$|c(V(G))| = \chi(G) = \omega(G).$$

PROOF. By definition,

$$\begin{aligned} \omega(G) &= \max\{|V(P)| : P \subseteq G \text{ is a complete subgraph}\} \\ &= \max\{|V(P)| : P \subseteq G, \forall a \neq b \in V(P), ab \in E(G)\} \\ &= \max\{|V(P)| : P \subseteq G, \forall a \neq b \in V(P), c(a) \neq c(b)\} = c(G) \end{aligned}$$

consider $\omega(G) \leq \chi(G) \leq |c(V(G))|$, Hence $\chi(G) = \omega(G) = |c(V(G))|$.

[PROPERTIES 2] If G is a special perfect graph with a special coloring c , then any induced subgraph $P \subseteq G$ is also a special perfect graph, and $c|_{V(P)}$ is a special coloring of P .

PROOF. $\forall a, b \in V(P), ab \in E(P) \iff ab \in E(G) \iff c(a) \neq c(b) \iff c|_{V(P)}(a) \neq c|_{V(P)}(b)$

P is also a special perfect graph, and $c|_{V(P)}$ is a special coloring of P .

[**PROPERTIES 3**] If G is a special perfect graph, then G is a perfect graph.

PROOF. For any induced subgraph $P \subseteq G$, by P is also special perfect, hence by **PROPERTIES 1** we have $\chi(P) = \omega(P)$. Therefore G is perfect.

[**PROPERTIES 4**] If G is a special perfect graph and c is its special coloring, then c is the unique optimal coloring of G (i.e., if c' is a coloring of G with $|c'(V(G))| = \chi(G)$, then $c' = c$ up to renaming of colors).which means G is uniquely colorable.

PROOF Let c, c' be two optimal colorings of G with $|c(V(G))| = |c'(V(G))| = \chi(G)$. Take a maximum complete subgraph $P \subseteq G$ with $|V(P)| = \omega(G) = \chi(G)$. Then on P every vertex must receive a distinct color under any optimal coloring, so after renaming colors we may assume $c|_{V(P)} = c'|_{V(P)}$. Now observe the two colorings on $V(G) \setminus V(P)$. For any $a \in V(G) \setminus V(P)$, since P is maximum, there exists $b \in V(P)$ such that $ab \notin E(G)$; hence by the defining property $ab \notin E(G) \iff c(a) = c(b)$, we must have $c(a) = c(b)$. Similarly $c'(a) = c'(b)$. Since $c(b) = c'(b)$, we get $c(a) = c'(a)$ for all $a \in V(G) \setminus V(P)$, hence $c = c'$. Therefore the minimum coloring is unique.

[**PROPERTIES 5**] There are infinitely many special perfect graphs except isolated points and complete graphs.

PROOF. Let A be a set of isolated vertices; define $c(a) = 1$ for all $a \in A$. Then A is a special perfect graph. Also, any complete graph K_n is special perfect: label $V(K_n) = \{x_1, \dots, x_n\}$ and define $c(x_i) = i$.

Now take two disjoint sets of vertices A, B with $|A| = n$ and $|B| = 1$. Define a graph G by $V(G) = A \cup B$ and

$$ab \in E(G) \iff (a \in A, b \in B) \text{ or } (a \in B, b \in A),$$

i.e., G is complete bipartite between A and B with no edges inside A or inside B . Define a coloring c by $c(x) = 1$ if $x \in A$ and $c(x) = 2$ if $x \in B$. Then

$$ab \in E(G) \iff c(a) \neq c(b),$$

so G is a special perfect graph. Varying $|A|$ gives infinitely many such graphs.

[**PROPERTIES 6**] Consider a graph G and subgraphs $P_1, \dots, P_k \subseteq G$. If $c : V(G) \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}^+$ is a coloring of G , then

$$|c(V(P_1)) \cap \dots \cap c(V(P_k))| \geq \omega(P_1 \cap \dots \cap P_k).$$

In particular, if G is a special perfect graph and c is its special coloring, then

$$|c(V(P_1)) \cap \dots \cap c(V(P_k))| \geq \omega(P_1 \cap \dots \cap P_k),$$

and the equality holds if and only if

$$\#\{x_1, \dots, x_k : \forall 1 \leq i \leq k, x_i \in V(P_i - \bigcap_{i=1}^k P_i), \forall y \in V(\bigcap_{i=1}^k P_i), yx_i \in E(G)\}$$

is an independant set.

PROOF. (1) $\forall G$ is a graph, c is a coloring of $G, \forall 1 \leq i \leq k, c(\bigcap_{i=1}^n P_i) \subseteq c(P_i)$, so

$$c(\bigcap_{i=1}^n P_i) \subseteq \bigcap_{i=1}^n c(P_i)$$

$$|\bigcap_{i=1}^n c(P_i)| \geq |c(\bigcap_{i=1}^n P_i)| \geq \chi(\bigcap_{i=1}^n P_i) \geq \omega(\bigcap_{i=1}^n P_i)$$

(2) if G is a special perfect graph, then the quality is not true

$$\iff \forall 1 \leq i \leq k, \exists x_i \in V(P_i - \bigcap_{i=1}^k P_i), \text{ s.t } c(x_i) \notin c(\bigcap_{i=1}^k P_i) \text{ and } c(x_1) = \dots = c(x_k)$$

$$\iff \exists \{x_1, \dots, x_k : \forall 1 \leq i \leq k, x_i \in V(P_i - \bigcap_{i=1}^k P_i), \forall y \in V(\bigcap_{i=1}^k P_i), yx_i \in E(G)\}$$

is an independent set so the equality holds \iff

$$\nexists \{x_1, \dots, x_k : \forall 1 \leq i \leq k, x_i \in V(P_i - \bigcap_{i=1}^k P_i), \forall y \in V(\bigcap_{i=1}^k P_i), yx_i \in E(G)\}$$

is an independent set.

[**PROPERTIES 7**]. The special perfect graph may not be a chordal graph, or a bipartite graph; its complement graph may also fail to be a comparability graph or a bipartite graph.

PROOF. We have proved that for any A_n (a set of isolated points) and $B = \{b\}$, the graph $A_n \vee B$ is a special perfect graph. Complete graphs are special perfect graphs, and all isolated-point graphs are special perfect graphs.

Consider a rectangle $abcd$ with a coloring $c(a) = c(c) = 1$ and $c(b) = c(d) = 2$. $\forall e, f$ are adjacent whenever $c(e) \neq c(f)$, then by definition c is a special coloring of $abcd$, hence $abcd$ is a special perfect graph. However, $abcd$ is not a chordal graph. Also, K_n is complete and hence not bipartite for $n \geq 3$, so a special perfect graph may not be bipartite. Moreover, if $n = 3$, $(A_n \vee B)^c$ is not a or a bipartite graph; thus the complement of a special perfect graph may fail to be bipartite.

[**PROPERTIES 8**]. The complement graph of a special perfect graph is chordal, but the complement graph of a chordal graph may not be a special perfect graph.

PROOF

- (1) If G is a special perfect graph, then for $a, b, c \in V(G)$ with $ab, ac \notin E(G)$ and $bc \in E(G)$, we get a contradiction by considering the special coloring of G : from $ab \in E(G)$ and $ac \in E(G)$ we must have $c(b) = c(a)$ and $c(c) = c(a)$, while $bc \in E(G)$ forces $c(b) \neq c(c)$ (under the special coloring), impossible.

If G is a special perfect graph and \overline{G} is not chordal, then \overline{G} contains an induced cycle x_1, \dots, x_n with $n \geq 4$. Hence in G we have $x_i x_{i+1} \notin E(G)$ (indices mod n) while all other pairs are edges, $x_1 x_2, x_2 x_3, x_3 x_4 \in E(G), x_1 x_3, x_2 x_4, x_1 x_4 \notin E(G)$, so $x_1 x_2, x_2 x_3, x_3 x_4 \notin E(\overline{G}), x_1 x_3, x_2 x_4, x_1 x_4 \in E(\overline{G})$, so $x_1 x_2, x_2 x_3 \notin E(G), x_1 x_3 \in E(G)$, G is not a special perfect graph, where's the contradiction. Therefore every special perfect graph is the complement of a chordal graph.

- (2) Consider deleting an edge from K_4 . The resulting graph G is chordal, may assume that $ab \notin E(G)$, $ab \in E(\overline{G})$, $ca \notin E(\overline{G})$, $cb \notin E(\overline{G})$, so \overline{G} is not a special perfect graph. Hence, the complement of a chordal graph may not be a special perfect graph.

[REMARK 1] For any graph G' , suppose G and K_n are subgraphs of G with $V(G) \cup V(K_n) = V(G')$ (and typically $V(G) \cap V(K_n) = \emptyset$). may assume $V(K_n) = \{x_1, \dots, x_n\}$, we have proved

$$\chi(G') = \chi(G)$$

if and only if there exists a coloring c of G with $|c(V(G))| = \chi(G)$ such that

$$\max_{1 \leq k \leq n, \{i_1, \dots, i_k\} \subseteq \{1, \dots, n\}} \left\{ \left| \bigcap_{p=1}^k c(L(x_{i_p})) \right| + k \right\} \leq \chi(G).$$

in particular, if G is a special perfect graph and

$$\nexists \{x_1, \dots, x_k : \forall 1 \leq i \leq k, x_i \in V(P_i - \bigcap_{i=1}^k P_i), \forall y \in V(\bigcap_{i=1}^k P_i), yx_i \in E(G)\}$$

then $\chi(G) = \chi(G') \iff \omega(G) = \omega(G')$

PROOF

$$\chi(G) = \chi(G')$$

$$\iff \exists c \text{ is a coloring of } G, |c(V(G))| = \chi(G)$$

such that

$$\max_{1 \leq k \leq n, \{i_1, \dots, i_k\} \subseteq \{1, \dots, n\}} \left\{ \left| \bigcap_{p=1}^k c(L(x_{i_p})) \right| + k \right\} \leq \chi(G).$$

$$\iff \exists c \text{ is a coloring of } G, |c(V(G))| = \chi(G)$$

such that

$$\max_{1 \leq k \leq n, \{i_1, \dots, i_k\} \subseteq \{1, \dots, n\}} \left\{ \omega\left(\bigcap_{p=1}^k L(x_{i_p})\right) + k \right\} \leq \omega(G).$$

$$\iff \max \left\{ \omega(G), \max_{1 \leq k \leq n, \{i_1, \dots, i_k\} \subseteq \{1, \dots, n\}} \left(\omega\left(\bigcap_{p=1}^k L(x_{i_p})\right) + k \right) \right\} = \omega(G)$$

$$\iff w(G') = w(G)$$

[EXAMPLE] Let K_n and K_m be complete graphs and G be a graph such that $V(K_m) \cup V(K_n) = V(G)$ and $V(K_m) \cap V(K_n) = \emptyset$. For any coloring c of G , we may assume the

restriction $c|_{V(K_m)}$ is unique (up to renaming of colors). Then

$$\begin{aligned}
\chi(G) &= \min\{|c(V(G))| : c \text{ is a coloring of } G\} \\
&= \min\{|c(V(G))| : c \text{ is a coloring of } G, c|_{K_m} = c|_{K_m}\} \\
&= \max\left\{|c(V(K_m))|, \max_{1 \leq k \leq n, \{i_1, \dots, i_k\} \subseteq \{1, \dots, n\}} \left\{ \left| \bigcap_{p=1}^k c(L(x_{i_p})) \right| + k \right\} \right\} \\
&= \max\left\{\omega(K_m), \max_{1 \leq k \leq n, \{i_1, \dots, i_k\} \subseteq \{1, \dots, n\}} \left\{ c\left(\bigcap_{p=1}^k L(x_{i_p})\right) + k \right\} \right\}. \\
&= \max\left\{\omega(K_m), \max_{1 \leq k \leq n, \{i_1, \dots, i_k\} \subseteq \{1, \dots, n\}} \left\{ \omega\left(\bigcap_{p=1}^k L(x_{i_p})\right) + k \right\} \right\}. \\
&= \omega(G)
\end{aligned}$$

REMARK. The graph G mentioned above may contain an odd cycle of length 5; according to the strong perfect graph theorem it may not be a perfect graph, but it still satisfies $\omega(G) = \chi(G)$. In fact, if a graph G has $\omega(G) \geq 5$, it is certainly not a perfect graph.

2 Calculate the chromatic number using matrix

[DEF] For a graph G , if there exist complete subgraphs $K_{n_1}, \dots, K_{n_p} \subseteq G$ such that

$$V(G) = V(K_{n_1}) \cup \dots \cup V(K_{n_p}), \forall 1 \leq i \neq j \leq p, V(K_{n_i}) \cap V(K_{n_j}) = \emptyset$$

then we call G a union of complete subgraphs (clique cover). and $\{K_{n_1}, K_{n_2}, \dots, K_{n_p}\}$ is called a decomposition of G .

Let $\{K_{n_1}, \dots, K_{n_p}\}$ be a clique cover of G (i.e., $V(G) = V(K_{n_1}) \cup \dots \cup V(K_{n_p})$). This decomposition is in general not unique; even if we choose it greedily (e.g. $|K_{n_1}| = \omega(G)$, $|K_{n_2}| = \omega(G - K_{n_1})$, ... $|K_{n_p}| = \omega(G - \cup_{i=1}^{p-1} K_{n_i})$), the family may still not be unique.

Fix an integer $m \in \mathbb{Z}^+$ with

$$m \geq \max\{|K_{n_1}|, \dots, |K_{n_p}|\}.$$

now define $\forall 1 \leq i \neq j \leq p$, $K_{n_i}^{(m)}$ is a complete graph

$$V(K_{n_i}) \subseteq V(K_{n_i}^{(m)}); V(K_{n_i}^{(m)}) \cap V(K_{n_j}^{(m)}) = \emptyset \quad (i \neq j)$$

Define a graph $\{K_{n_1}, \dots, K_{n_p}\}^{(m)}$ with vertex set

$$V(\{K_{n_1}, \dots, K_{n_p}\}^{(m)}) := V(K_{n_1}^{(m)}) \cup \dots \cup V(K_{n_p}^{(m)}),$$

and with edges given by

$$ab \in E(\{K_{n_1}, \dots, K_{n_p}\}^{(m)}) \iff (ab \in E(G)) \text{ or } (\exists i, a, b \in V(K_{n_i}^{(m)})).$$

We call $\{K_{n_1}, \dots, K_{n_p}\}^{(m)}$ the graph induced by the decomposition and the integer m .

[REMARK 1] Let G be a graph and $\{K_{n_1}, \dots, K_{n_p}\}$ be a clique cover of G . Then G is m -colorable if and only if $\{K_{n_1}, \dots, K_{n_p}\}^{(m)}$ is m -colorable.

PROOF. If $\{K_{n_1}, \dots, K_{n_p}\}^{(m)}$ is m -colorable, then its restriction to $V(G) \subseteq V(\{K_{n_1}, \dots, K_{n_p}\}^{(m)})$ gives an m -coloring of G . Conversely, if G is m -colorable, take a coloring c of G with $|c(V(G))| \leq m$. Define c' on $\{K_{n_1}, \dots, K_{n_p}\}^{(m)}$ by setting $c'(a) = c(a)$ for $a \in V(G)$, and for each added vertex $a \in V(K_{n_i}^{(m)}) \setminus V(K_{n_i})$ choose $c'(a)$ so that all vertices in the complete graph $K_{n_i}^{(m)}$ receive distinct colors; then $c'(\{K_{n_1}, \dots, K_{n_p}\}^{(m)}) = m$, $\forall a, b \in V(\{K_{n_1}, \dots, K_{n_p}\}^{(m)})$, if $ab \in E(G)$, $c'(a) = c(a) \neq c(b) = c'(b)$, if $ab \notin E(G)$, $\exists 1 \leq i \leq p$, $ab \in E(K_{n_i}^{(m)})$, $c'(a) \neq c'(b)$, c' is a coloring of $\{K_{n_1}, \dots, K_{n_p}\}^{(m)}$.

[REMARK 2] Let G be a graph and $\{K_{n_1}, \dots, K_{n_p}\}$ be a clique cover of G . Then for any $m \geq \max\{|K_{n_1}|, \dots, |K_{n_p}|\}$, G is m -colorable

$$\begin{aligned} &\iff \exists \{K'_1, \dots, K'_m\} \text{ such that each } K'_i \subseteq \{K_{n_1}, \dots, K_{n_p}\}^{(m)} \text{ is complete,} \\ &\quad V(K'_1) \cup \dots \cup V(K'_m) = V(\{K_{n_1}, \dots, K_{n_p}\}^{(m)}), \forall i \neq j, V(K'_i) \cap V(K'_j) = \emptyset. \end{aligned}$$

PROOF

$$\begin{aligned} &G \text{ is } m\text{-colorable} \iff \{K_{n_1}, \dots, K_{n_p}\}^{(m)} \text{ is } m\text{-colorable} \\ &\iff \exists c \text{ a coloring of } \{K_{n_1}, \dots, K_{n_p}\}^{(m)} \text{ s.t. } |c(V(\{K_{n_1}, \dots, K_{n_p}\}^{(m)}))| = m \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\iff \exists \{K'_1, \dots, K'_m\} \text{ such that each } K'_i \subseteq \overline{\{K_{n_1}, \dots, K_{n_p}\}^{(m)}} \text{ is complete,} \\ &\quad V(K'_1) \cup \dots \cup V(K'_m) = V(\overline{\{K_{n_1}, \dots, K_{n_p}\}^{(m)}}), \forall i \neq j, V(K'_i) \cap V(K'_j) = \emptyset. \end{aligned}$$

[CONVENTION]. Denote $\overline{\{K_{n_1}, \dots, K_{n_p}\}^{(m)}}$ by G' .

[DEF 1]. Consider a function $A(\sigma_k) \in \mathbb{Z}$, with $1 \leq i_1, \dots, i_p \leq n$. $\sigma = \{\sigma_1, \sigma_2, \dots, \sigma_m\}$, $\forall 1 \leq k_1 \neq k_2 \leq m, \forall 1 \leq z \leq p, \sigma_{k_1}(i_z) \neq \sigma_{k_2}(i_z)$ with $\sigma_k : \{i_1, \dots, i_p\} \rightarrow \{1, \dots, m\}$ define

$$\text{perm } A := \sum_{\sigma} \prod_{k=1}^m A(\sigma_k).$$

Assume

$$V(K_{n_i}^{(m)}) = \{x_{i,1}, \dots, x_{i,m}\} \quad (1 \leq i \leq p).$$

Define $d((i_1, j_1), (i_2, j_2)) \in \{0, 1\}$ by

$$d((i_1, j_1), (i_2, j_2)) = \begin{cases} 1, & x_{i_1, j_1} x_{i_2, j_2} \in E(G'), \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Define $A(\sigma_k) \in \{0, 1\}$ by

$$A(\sigma_k) = \prod_{1 \leq r \neq s \leq p} d((r, \sigma_k(r)), (s, \sigma_k(s))).$$

then

$$\text{perm } A := \sum_{\sigma} \prod_{k=1}^p A(\sigma_k) = \sum_{\sigma} \prod_{k=1}^p \prod_{1 \leq r \neq s \leq p} d((r, \sigma_k(r)), (s, \sigma_k(s)))$$

We call $\text{perm } A$ the permanent associated to G' .

[PROPOSITION]. For G' , the $\text{perm } A$ equals $|\{c : c \text{ is a coloring of } G' \text{ and } |c(G')| = m\}| * n!$.

PROOF. $\forall \sigma = (\sigma_1, \dots, \sigma_m)$, one has

$$\prod_{k=1}^p A(\sigma_k) = 1 \iff \forall 1 \leq k \leq m, \forall 1 \leq r \neq s \leq p, d((r, \sigma_k(r)), (s, \sigma_k(s))) = 1$$

$$\iff \exists \{K'_1, \dots, K'_m\} \text{ such that each } K'_i \subseteq \overline{\{K_{n_1}, \dots, K_{n_p}\}^{(m)}} \text{ is complete,} \\ V(K'_1) \cup \dots \cup V(K'_m) = V(\overline{\{K_{n_1}, \dots, K_{n_p}\}^{(m)}}), \forall i \neq j, V(K'_i) \cap V(K'_j) = \emptyset.$$

with σ_k to K'_k

$$\iff \sigma \text{ is a coloring of } G' \text{ with } \sigma_k \text{ is the } k\text{-th color}$$

thus

$$\text{perm } A = |\{c : c \text{ is a coloring of } G' \text{ and } |c(G')| = m\}| * n!$$

[DEDUCTION]. Let G be a graph and $\{K_{n_1}, \dots, K_{n_p}\}$ be a decomposition (clique cover) of G . Then

$$\begin{aligned} \chi(G) &= \min\{m : G \text{ is } m\text{-colorable}\} \\ &= \min\{m : \{K_{n_1}, \dots, K_{n_p}\}^{(m)} \text{ is } m\text{-colorable}\} \\ &= \min\{m : \exists c \text{ a coloring of } G', |c(G')| = m\} \\ &= \min\{m : |\{c : c \text{ is a coloring of } G' \text{ and } |c(G')| = m\}| > 0\} \\ &= \min\{m : \text{perm}(\{K_{n_1}, \dots, K_{n_p}\}^{(m)}) > 0\}. \end{aligned}$$

[DEF]. To simplify the question, we consider the graph G' which has the form mentioned above. Assume there exist independent sets $K_1^1, \dots, K_{n_1}^1, K_1^2, \dots, K_{n_2}^2, \dots, K_1^p, \dots, K_{n_p}^p$ such that

$$|V(K_j^i)| = m, \quad V(G^*) = \bigcup_{i=1}^p \bigcup_{j=1}^{n_i} V(K_j^i), \quad V(K_{j_1}^{i_1}) \cap V(K_{j_2}^{i_2}) = \emptyset \text{ if } (i_1, j_1) \neq (i_2, j_2)$$

$$\forall 1 \leq i \leq p, \sigma^i = \{\sigma_{k_1}^i, \dots, \sigma_{k_m}^i\} \text{ with } \sigma_{k_k}^i : \{1, \dots, n_i\} \rightarrow \{1, \dots, m\}$$

$$\forall 1 \leq k_1 \neq k_2 \leq m, \forall 1 \leq z \leq n_i, \sigma_{k_1}^i(z) \neq \sigma_{k_2}^i(z)$$

$$\forall 1 \leq i_1 \neq i_2 \leq p, \forall 1 \leq k_1, k_2 \leq m, \prod_{1 \leq r \leq n_{i_1}, 1 \leq s \leq n_{i_2}} d((r, \sigma_{k_1}^{i_1}(r)), (s, \sigma_{k_2}^{i_2}(s)))$$

is denoted by $B(\sigma_{k_1}^{i_1}, \sigma_{k_2}^{i_2})$

more generally, $\forall i_1 \neq i_2 \neq \dots \neq i_q \subseteq \{1, \dots, p\}, k_1, \dots, k_q \subseteq \{1, \dots, m\}$,

$$\prod_{1 \leq a \neq b \leq q} B(\sigma_{k_a}^{i_a}, \sigma_{k_b}^{i_b}) \text{ is denoted by } B(\sigma_{k_1}^{i_1}, \dots, \sigma_{k_q}^{i_q})$$

in particular,

$$\prod_{k=1}^m B(\sigma_k^{i_1}, \dots, \sigma_k^{i_q}) \text{ is denoted by } B(\sigma^{i_1}, \dots, \sigma^{i_q});$$

$$\prod_{k=1}^m A(\sigma_{i_1}^k) \text{ is denoted by } A(\sigma^{i_1})$$

[PROPOSITION]. For G' mentioned above,

$$\text{perm}(G') = \sum_{\sigma^1} \cdots \sum_{\sigma^q} \prod_{i=1}^p A(\sigma^i) \cdot B(\sigma^1, \dots, \sigma^p).$$

PROOF.

(1) Consider a map

$$f : \{\sigma^1, \dots, \sigma^q\} \longrightarrow \left\{ (\sigma_k^1 \cup \dots \cup \sigma_k^q)_{1 \leq k \leq m} \right\},$$

where for each $1 \leq i \leq q$, σ^i is a division of the i -th part.

$$\begin{aligned} \forall 1 \leq j' \leq \prod q * n_q, \exists 1 \leq i \leq p, 1 \leq j \leq n_i, \forall 1 \leq k \leq m, (\sigma_k^1 \cup \dots \cup \sigma_k^q)(j') &= \sigma_k^i(j) \\ \implies \forall 1 \leq k_1 \neq k_2 \leq m, (\sigma_{k_1}^1 \cup \dots \cup \sigma_{k_1}^q)(j') &= \sigma_{k_1}^i(j) \neq \sigma_{k_2}^i(j) = (\sigma_{k_2}^1 \cup \dots \cup \sigma_{k_2}^q)(j') \\ &\implies f \text{ is well defined} \end{aligned}$$

(2) consider $\forall \sigma$

$$\begin{aligned} \forall 1 \leq i \leq p, \forall 1 \leq k_1 \neq k_2 \leq m, \forall 1 \leq j \leq n_i, \\ \sigma_{k_1}|_{\{K_1^i \cup \dots \cup K_{n_i}^i\}}(j) = \sigma_{k_1}(j') \neq \sigma_{k_2}(j') = \sigma_{k_2}|_{\{K_1^i \cup \dots \cup K_{n_i}^i\}}(j) \\ \implies \exists \left\{ \sigma|_{\{K_1^1 \cup \dots \cup K_{n_1}^1\}}, \dots, \sigma|_{\{K_1^i \cup \dots \cup K_{n_i}^i\}} \right\} s.t \\ f\left(\left\{ \sigma|_{\{K_1^1 \cup \dots \cup K_{n_1}^1\}}, \dots, \sigma|_{\{K_1^i \cup \dots \cup K_{n_i}^i\}} \right\}\right) = \sigma \text{ and it's unique} \end{aligned}$$

Hence f is well-defined and is a bijection.

Therefore

$$\begin{aligned} \text{perm}(G') &= \sum_{\sigma} A(\sigma) = \sum_{\sigma} \prod_{k=1}^p \prod_{1 \leq j'_1 \neq j'_2 \leq p} d((j'_1, \sigma_k(j'_1)), (j'_2, \sigma_k(j'_2))) \\ &= \sum_{\sigma} \prod_{k=1}^m \left\{ \prod_{i=1}^p \prod_{1 \leq j_1 \neq j_2 \leq n_i} d((j_1, \sigma_k|_{\{K_1^i \cup \dots \cup K_{n_i}^i\}}(j_1)), (j_2, \sigma_k|_{\{K_1^i \cup \dots \cup K_{n_i}^i\}}(j_2))) \right\} \\ & * \left[\prod_{1 \leq i_1 \neq i_2 \leq p} \prod_{1 \leq j_1 \leq n_{i_1}, 1 \leq j_2 \leq n_{i_2}} d((j_1, \sigma_k|_{\{K_1^{i_1} \cup \dots \cup K_{n_{i_1}}^{i_1}\}}(j_1)), (j_2, \sigma_k|_{\{K_1^{i_2} \cup \dots \cup K_{n_{i_2}}^{i_2}\}}(j_2))) \right] \\ &= \sum_{\sigma^1} \sum_{\sigma^2} \cdots \sum_{\sigma^p} \prod_{k=1}^m \left\{ \prod_{i=1}^p \prod_{1 \leq j_1 \neq j_2 \leq n_i} d((j_1, \sigma_k^i(j_1)), (j_2, \sigma_k^i(j_2))) \right\} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& * \left[\prod_{1 \leq i_1 \neq i_2 \leq p} \prod_{1 \leq j_1 \leq n_{i_1}, 1 \leq j_2 \leq n_{i_2}} d((j_1, \sigma_k^{i_1}(j_1)), (j_2, \sigma_k^{i_2}(j_2))) \right] \} \\
& = \sum_{\sigma^1} \sum_{\sigma^2} \dots \sum_{\sigma^p} \left[\prod_{i=1}^p \prod_{k=1}^m \prod_{1 \leq j_1 \neq j_2 \leq n_i} d((j_1, \sigma_k^i(j_1)), (j_2, \sigma_k^i(j_2))) \right] \\
& * \left[\prod_{k=1}^m \prod_{1 \leq i_1 \neq i_2 \leq p} \prod_{1 \leq j_1 \leq n_{i_1}, 1 \leq j_2 \leq n_{i_2}} d((j_1, \sigma_k^{i_1}(j_1)), (j_2, \sigma_k^{i_2}(j_2))) \right] \\
& = \sum_{\sigma^1} \dots \sum_{\sigma^q} \prod_{i=1}^p A(\sigma^i) \cdot B(\sigma^1, \dots, \sigma^p)
\end{aligned}$$

[DEDUCTION]. If $p = 2$, then

$$\text{perm}(G') = \sum_{\sigma^1} \sum_{\sigma^2} A(\sigma_1)A(\sigma_2)B(\sigma_1, \sigma_2) = [\mathbf{A}(\boldsymbol{\sigma}_1)]^T M_{B(\sigma_1, \sigma_2)} \mathbf{A}(\boldsymbol{\sigma}_2)$$

Therefore, the *arbitrary connections* of two graphs can be regarded as adding a matrix (encoding the interaction between the two parts).

[OPEN PROBLEMS]. This paper originated from the author's reflections on the four-color problem; however, the analysis and characterization of forbidden subgraphs turns out to be rather difficult.

No further specific research was conducted on the properties of the graph as proposed in the text.

No further specific research was conducted on the properties of the permanent as proposed in the text.